

The School Leadership and Teacher's Autonomy on Curriculum Implementation of Public Secondary School Teachers

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Abstract. The issue to which school leadership may be either facilitating or restricting teacher's autonomy over their curriculum and teaching methodologies is critical for the ultimate goal of education which is to provide quality of learning outcomes. This study utilized a non-experimental quantitative research methodology using a descriptive correlation approach was applied. Statistical analyses such as the mean, Pearson R correlation, and Multiple Linear Regression were utilized. The participants in the research were one hundred twenty (120) public secondary school educators conveniently selected secondary schools in Tugbok District, Division of Davao City. Descriptive results of the study revealed that the extent of school leadership received a high descriptive level rating which means that the extent of school leadership as perceived by public secondary school teachers is often evident while the extent of teacher's autonomy on curriculum implementation received a high descriptive level rating which means that the extent of autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers is often evident. Consequently, there is a strong positive significant relationship between the school leadership and the teacher's autonomy on curriculum implementation. Furthermore, the instructional leadership, crisis management and data-driven decision making indicators of school leadership significantly influenced the autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teacher.

KEY WORDS

1. Educational Excellence 2. Conflict Resolution Strategies 3. Public
Secondary School Teachers

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1. Introduction

Education is a cornerstone of societal development, and the quality of education is significantly influenced by the leadership within educational institutions and the autonomy afforded to teachers in curriculum implementation. With this, the effective implementation of the curriculum that is supported with good and effective leadership is crucial in ensuring that students receive a high-quality education that equips them with the necessary knowledge and skills for the future. However, striking a balance between teacher autonomy and adhering to a prescribed curriculum is a challenging task, one which is invariably affected by the leadership style and decisions of the school's management. The issue to which school leadership may be either facilitating or restricting teacher's autonomy over their curriculum and teaching methodologies is critical for the ultimate goal of education which is to provide quality of learning outcomes.

Consequently, the role of leadership in education, especially school leadership, has been acknowledged as fundamental in shaping the direction, culture, and overall success of educational institutions (Leithwood Riehl, 2013). A school's leadership style with such skills like instructional leadership, effective communication, data-driven decision making, and crisis management can significantly influence the level of autonomy afforded to teachers in terms of instructional strategies, assessment and evaluation, curriculum adaptation, and reflective practice in their classrooms, which in turn, can have profound implications on curriculum implementation. As Fullan and Hargreaves (2016) argued, the relationship between leadership and curriculum implementation is pivotal in the realization of school reform efforts. Globally, public secondary schools confront an array of challenges in curriculum implementation due to factors like diverse pedagogical beliefs, the integration of modern classroom technology, large class sizes, and the emphasis on socio-emotional learning (SEL). With this, the variations in teaching approaches can affect consistent educational experiences, making it crucial for leadership to promote collaborative platforms where strategies align with curricular demands (Darling-Hammond Hyler, 2017). Moreover, the push for digital tool inclusion highlights the importance of leadership supporting professional development, considering the significant role of teachers' beliefs in effective technology integration (Ertmer et al., 2014). In addition, the dynamics of managing large classrooms further emphasize the need for leadership to equip educators with effective management tools, strategies, and support, ensuring individualized attention (Hattie, 2015). Lastly, as schools gravitate towards holistic student development, leadership must prioritize training in SEL, allowing teachers the autonomy to weave these elements into their lessons, enhancing both academic and life skills outcomes (Durlak et al., 2018). In the Philippines, public secondary schools navigate complex challenges in curriculum implementation, influenced by factors like the transition to the K-12 system, geographical disparities and the country's ethno-linguistic diversity. The introduction of the K-12 education framework necessitated swift curricular and pedagogical adjustments, with educators requiring substantial support from leadership to adapt effectively (Bautista, Bernardo, Ocampo, 2017). Another, the nation's unique geographical and cultural disparities, particularly in the remote islands, can impede access to standardized educational resources, necessitating adaptability in curriculum delivery (Arinto, Cadao, Abdon, 2018). Lastly, with the Philippines' vast linguistic diversity, it's imperative for school leadership to prioritize curriculum localization while granting teachers autonomy to tailor lessons to students' cultural contexts (Sibayan, 2015). Furthermore, the nation's susceptibility to natural calamities calls for adaptive curriculum strategies and leadership that emphasizes flexibility, ensuring educational continuity (Mendoza, Uy, Mirandilla-Santos, 2017). Locally, public secondary schools, in general, face a unique set of challenges when it comes to curriculum implementation. They cater to a diverse set of students and are often required to adhere to strict national or state-level curricular mandates. For these schools, understanding the dynamics between leadership styles and teacher autonomy can be the key to successful curriculum implementation (Reyes, 2019). Additionally, in an era where educational reforms are being pushed with an emphasis on standardization and accountability, the autonomy of public secondary school teachers has come under scrutiny. The role of school leadership in either facilitating or restricting this autonomy is crucial for the ultimate goal of improving student outcomes (Buendia, 2020). Thus, given the above considerations, a comprehensive study on the interplay between school leadership and teacher

autonomy in the context of curriculum implementation in public secondary schools becomes imperative. By exploring this relationship, educational stakeholders can gain valuable insights to foster environments where both leadership and teachers collaboratively work towards the best outcomes for students.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the research methods in conducting the study which are considered strategies or techniques utilized in the collection of data evidence for analysis in order to uncover new information or create better understanding of a topic. Contents of this chapter include the research design, research respondents of the study, research instrument and the data gathering procedures. It's also crucial to acknowledge that the researcher employed artificial intelligence technology to meticulously proofread the article, demonstrating an exemplary commitment to ethical standards in today's rapidly advancing AI landscape.

2.1. Research Design—In this study, the researcher used a descriptive correlational strategy for non-experimental quantitative research. The descriptive design explains the researched population, circumstance, or phenomena. It emphasizes on addressing the how, what, when, and where questions rather than the why of a research topic (Babbie, 2016). This design is important to the research because it specifies the techniques and processes for gathering the necessary information, as well as the general operational pattern or framework of the project, which dictates what information is to be acquired from which sources using which methods (Fox 2015). In particular, the descriptive part of the said research design will be used in assessing the extent of school leadership as perceived by the teachers in terms of instructional leadership, effective communication, data-driven decision making, and crisis management as well as the extent of teacher's autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers in Tugbok District, Division of Davao City in terms of instructional strategies, assessment and evaluation, curriculum adaptation, and reflective practice. On the other hand, the correlational research design part of this study is a methodological approach used in scientific research to examine the relationships or associations between two or more variables. It aims to determine whether changes in one variable are associated with changes in another variable without establishing causation. In a correlational study, researchers collect data on the variables of interest and then use statistical techniques to analyze the strength and direction of the relationships between these variables (Bordens, 2019). Specifically, this study will employ the said design since it wants to determine the significant relationship between the school leadership as perceived by the teachers and teacher autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers in Tugbok District, Division of Davao City as well as prove if there is an indicator of school leadership that significantly influence the teacher autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers the said district.

2.2. Research Respondents—The conduct of this study will be held on the selected secondary schools in Tugbok District, Division of Davao City. There will be one hundred and twenty (120) secondary level educators that will serve as the responders in this research. The respondents will be selected using a convenience sampling, which is the most common method of selection that does not rely on probability, will be used to choose them. This type of sampling

method is used for collecting samples that involves getting samples from sources of data that are easily located or that provide researchers convenience (Edgar and Manz, 2017).

2.3. *Research Instrument*—Developing research instruments is a critical step in the research process as they serve as the means to collect data and gather information from participants. These instruments play a pivotal role in ensuring the quality and validity of research findings. Well-designed research instruments help researchers measure variables accurately, leading to reliable data (Babbie, 2016). Moreover, they allow for the standardization of data collection, enabling the replication of studies and comparison of results across different contexts (Neuman, 2014). In this investigation, the researcher will use a survey questionnaire as its instrument in gathering its data. The survey questionnaire will have two parts that would cater the two variables in the study. Relatively, careful instrument development also promotes construct validity by ensuring that the items or questions included align with the intended constructs or concepts under investigation (Devellis, 2017). Additionally, clear and concise research instruments enhance participants’ un-

derstanding and cooperation, which is crucial for obtaining high-quality data (Dillman et al., 2014). Ultimately, the development of research instruments contributes to the credibility and rigor of research findings, making it an essential aspect of the research process. Specifically, validity of the instrument will be assured by research expert and members of the panel committee. The survey instrument also will be subjected for pilot testing in order to determine its reliability. This will be computed using the value of the instrument’s Cronbach’s Alpha. For the first part of the survey instrument, this would provide data on school leadership as perceived by the teachers in terms of instructional leadership, effective communication, data-driven decision making, and crisis management. Questions from this part of the instrument were adopted from the The Caring School Leadership Questionnaire (CSLQ) by Vyver, Westhuizen Meyer (2014). In the process of interpreting its data, a five-point Likert Scale of the survey having five (5) as the highest and one (1) as the lowest. The scale with description and interpretation is shown below. The following five order gradations with their respective range of means and description were considered:

Range, Descriptive Equivalent, and Interpretation of School Leadership Perception by Teachers

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20–5.00	Very High	This means that the school leadership as perceived by the teachers is always evident.
3.40–4.19	High	This means that the school leadership as perceived by the teachers is often evident.
2.60–3.39	Moderate	This means that the school leadership as perceived by the teachers is sometimes evident.
1.80–2.59	Low	This means that the school leadership as perceived by the teachers is seldom evident.
1.00–1.79	Very Low	This means that the school leadership as perceived by the teachers is not evident.

For the second part of the questionnaire, this will determine the data on the teaching quality of public secondary school teachers. In this part, the researcher adopted the study of Yildiz, B., Günay, G. Özbilen (2021) on Evaluation of Teachers' Motivation and Curriculum Autonomy Levels. The same with the first part of the

survey questionnaire, a five-point Likert Scale of the survey having five (5) as the highest and one (1) as the lowest in interpreting its data. The scale with description and interpretation is shown below. The following five order gradations with their respective range of means and description were considered:

Range, Descriptive Level, and Interpretation of Autonomy on Curriculum Implementation by Public Secondary School Teachers

Range	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20–5.00	Very High	This means that the autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers is always evident.
3.40–4.19	High	This means that the autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers is often evident.
2.60–3.39	Moderate	This means that the autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers is sometimes evident.
1.80–2.59	Low	This means that the autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers is seldom evident.
1.00–1.79	Very Low	This means that the autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers is not evident.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—At the outset of the data gathering procedure, the researcher will write a letter seeking permission from the Dean of the Graduate School so that this research study will be conducted. Next, the researcher will secure a letter asking for permission to the Schools Division Superintendent, Division of Davao City through the channels of the Office of Public Schools District Supervisors (PSDS) of the selected different schools. Upon approval of the permit, the survey questionnaire will be ready for the conduct of the study. During the conduct of the study, the researcher will

personally hand-in the survey questionnaire to the selected respondents. The questionnaire will be retrieved right after the respondents will be done answering the survey questions. The researcher will still ensure that the collection and retrieval of data will be conducted following the IATF protocols for face-to-face learning delivery mode. Lastly, the collected data will be analyzed by a statistician using the different measures of treating the data as presented this chapter. The results in the treatment of the data were interpreted for further information of the study.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—

The study will use the respondents' collected data for analysis. The following statistical tools will be used in the analysis and interpretation of the responses in this study: The first step in the statistical analysis involves descriptive statistics particularly determining its central tendency through mean analysis to examine the extent of the administrator's ethical leadership and the teaching quality of public secondary school teachers. The mean is commonly used to measure the central tendency. Central tendency identifies a single value as representative of an entire distribution. It also provides an accurate description of the entire data (Creswell, 2013). In this study, the mean scores will be calculated for each indicator of school leadership as perceived by the teacher (instructional leadership, effective communication, data-driven decision making, and crisis management) and for each indicator of teacher's autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers (instructional strategies, assessment and evaluation, curriculum adaptation, and reflective practice). This analysis helps establish a baseline understanding of the variables before exploring their relationships further (Hair et al., 2019). To investigate the significant relationship between the school leadership as perceived by the teachers and teacher autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers, a correlation analysis can be employed. This statistical test reflects the strength and/or direction of the relationship between two (or more) variables. The direction of a correlation can be either positive or negative (Mukaka, 2012). The correlation analysis using the technique such as Pearson's correlation coefficient, can assess the strength and direction of associations between each of the indicator school leadership as perceived by the teacher (instructional leadership, effective communication, data-driven decision making, and crisis management) and teacher's autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers. If significant correlations are found, Multiple Regression Analysis (MLR) can be used to determine which specific indicator school leadership have the most substantial influence on teacher's autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers. This analysis can provide insights into which indicator of school leadership such as instructional leadership, effective communication, data-driven decision making, and crisis management are most critical for enhancing the teacher's autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers. However, it is also essential to control for potential confounding variables that may influence teacher's autonomy on curriculum implementation.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results and discussions based on the data gathered after the conduct of this study. This includes the interpretation of the data and the repercussions of the findings of the study. The deliberations presented in this chapter are aligned to the statement of the problem cited in the previous chapters of this study. Specifically, the presentation for the results and discussions in this study started from the extent of school leadership as perceived by the teachers in terms of instructional leadership, effective communication, data-driven decision making, and crisis management. This was followed by the extent of teacher's autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers in Tugbok District, Division of Davao City in terms of as well as its indicators such as the instructional strategies, assessment and evaluation, curriculum adaptation, and reflective practice. Next, was the discussion of the results of the significant

relationship between the school leadership and the autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers in Tugbok District, Division of Davao City. Lastly, the discussion of results on which indicator of school leadership as perceived by the teachers in terms of instructional leadership, effective communication, data-driven decision making, and crisis management significantly influence the autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers in Tugbok District, Division of Davao City.

Summary of the Extent of School Leadership Shown in Table 1 is the summary of the extent of school leadership as perceived by public secondary school teachers in Tugbok District, Division of Davao City which entails the strategic shaping and implementation of a vision that drives academic excellence, fosters a positive learning environment, and advocates for holistic student development (Ingersoll, Sirinides, Dougherty, 2018). It presented also in the same table are the indicators of educational excellence such as instructional leadership, effective communication, data-driven decision making, and crisis management.

Table 1. Summary of the Extent of School Leadership

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Level
Instructional Leadership	4.00	High
Effective Communication	3.67	High
Data-Driven Decision Making	3.57	High
Crises Management	3.84	High
Overall	3.77	High

Based on the analysis, the overall mean rating of the extent of school leadership as perceived by public secondary school teachers obtained a mean rating score of 3.77. This numerical data result is equivalent to a “high” descriptive level rating which means that the extent of school leadership as perceived by public secondary school teachers is often evident. This further suggests that leadership qualities and practices, spanning various domains such as instructional leadership, communication, data-driven decision-making, crisis management, and more, are consistently recognized by teachers. The implication is that the perceived high level of school leadership contributes positively to the overall educational environment, fostering a culture of collaboration, trust, and effective management within the school community. Relatively, this high overall mean score rating for the

extent of school leadership, as perceived by public secondary school teachers, aligns with the cited literatures highlighting the crucial role of effective leadership in schools. A study by Leithwood et al., (2016) emphasizes that leadership is a key factor influencing the overall school environment and student outcomes. Their study suggests that leadership practices, such as creating a positive school climate and fostering teacher collaboration, contribute to improved student achievement. Moreover, Hallinger and Heck (2020) also argue that effective leadership is essential for school improvement and student success. Their meta-analysis of research on school leadership highlights the positive correlation between leadership practices and student achievement. Delving to the details of the analysis of the extent of school leadership as perceived by public secondary school teachers, the

“Instructional Leadership” indicator of the educational excellence of public secondary school teachers ranked on top with a mean score rating of 4.00. This statistical result is equivalent to a “high” descriptive level rating which means that the instructional leadership of the leaders as part of their school leadership as perceived by the teachers is often evident. The implication is that a strong focus on instructional leadership contributes to a positive school culture and effective teaching practices, as reflected in the consistently high ratings provided by teachers. This aligns with existing literature highlighting the crucial role of instructional leadership in shaping school effectiveness and teacher professional development. A meta-analysis by Leithwood et al., (2014) supports these findings, indicating that high perceived instructional leadership correlates with positive educational outcomes. Additionally, a longitudinal study by Marks and Printy (2013) underscores the long-term benefits of effective instructional leadership, showing sustained improvement in teacher performance and student achievement over time.

Summary of the Extent of Autonomy on Curriculum Implementation of Public Secondary School Teachers

Shown in Table 2 is the summary of the extent of autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers which

refers to the degree of freedom and discretion teachers have in tailoring the curriculum to best fit the unique needs of their students and the specific contexts of their classrooms. Grounded in the premise that educators, as the immediate facilitators of learning, are most familiar with their students’ backgrounds, strengths, and challenges, such autonomy enables a more personalized, flexible, and effective approach to instruction (Woods, 2016). Consequently, presented also in the same table are the indicators of teacher’s autonomy on curriculum implementation such as instructional strategies, assessment and evaluation, curriculum adaptation, and reflective practice. Based on the analysis, the overall mean rating of the extent of autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers obtained a rating score of 3.99. This numerical data result is equivalent to a “high” descriptive level rating which means that the extent of autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers is often evident. This further suggests that teachers have a substantial degree of independence in shaping curriculum-related decisions and instructional strategies. The finding implies that educational policies and practices in the studied context support a culture of autonomy, potentially contributing to a diverse and flexible educational environment.

Table 2. Summary of the Extent of Autonomy on Curriculum Implementation of Public Secondary School Teachers

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Level
Instructional Strategies	4.02	High
Assessment and Evaluation	3.86	High
Curriculum Adaptation	3.91	High
Reflective Practice	4.16	High
Overall	3.99	High

Relatively, the overall mean rating for the extent of autonomy on curriculum implementation among public secondary school teachers aligns with the literature emphasizing the importance of teacher autonomy in fostering effective and innovative teaching practices. Autonomy in curriculum implementation allows teachers the flexibility to tailor their instructional strategies to meet the diverse needs of their students. In a study by Ingersoll and Strong (2015), teacher autonomy is identified as a critical factor influencing job satisfaction and retention. Teachers who perceive a high level of autonomy are more likely to feel empowered, leading to increased job satisfaction and commitment to their profession. In addition, a study also by Harris and Jones (2020) highlights the positive impact of teacher autonomy on student outcomes. Teachers who have the freedom to adapt and innovate in their instructional practices can create more engaging and effective learning experiences for their students. Delving the details of the analysis, the “Reflective Practice” indicator of the autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers ranked on top with a mean score rating of 4.16. This statistical result is equivalent to a “high” descriptive level rating which means that the reflective practice autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers is often evident. This implies that teachers enjoy freedom and support to participate in reflective practices, enabling critical evaluation and enhancement of instructional methods. This aligns with literature highlighting the importance of reflective practice in teaching and learning, involving teachers critically examining their teaching methods and outcomes. Schön (2013) introduced reflection-in-action and reflection-on-action, emphasizing ongoing reflection as part of professional development. Autonomy in reflective practices al-

lows teachers to engage in continuous improvement, adapting instructional strategies to better meet student needs.

Significant Relationship between the School Leadership and Autonomy on Curriculum Implementation of Public Secondary School Teachers

One of the aims of this study is to investigate the correlation between the school leadership and the autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers in Tugbok District, Division of Davao City. The Pearson correlation coefficient (r) is a suitable statistical analysis method for examining the presented data, as it is commonly employed to assess the presence of a significant association between the means of two distinct groups (Creswell Poth, 2016). The significance level for this study is established at 0.05. Shown in Table 3 is the statistical analysis on the significant relationship between the school leadership and the autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers in Tugbok District, Division of Davao City. The overall p-value is equal to 0.000 with an r-value equal to 0.759. This means that there is a strong positive significant relationship between the school leadership and the autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers in Tugbok District, Division of Davao City. Hence, this study rejects its established null hypothesis. The analysis further implies that effective school leadership positively influences the degree of autonomy teachers experience in curriculum implementation. The rejection of the null hypothesis suggests that there is indeed a meaningful and impactful association between school leadership and teachers’ autonomy in shaping curriculum strategies.

Table 3. Significant Relationship between the School Leadership and Autonomy on Curriculum Implementation of Public Secondary School Teachers

School Leadership	r	p-value	Decision on H0
Instructional Leadership	0.660	0.000	Reject
Effective Communication	0.524	0.000	Reject
Data-Driven Decision Making	0.424	0.000	Reject
Crisis Management	0.634	0.000	Reject
Overall	0.759	0.000	Reject

Relatively, the statistically significant relationship between school leadership and teacher autonomy on curriculum implementation is supported by existing literatures in educational leadership. Effective school leadership plays a crucial role in shaping the professional environment and influencing teachers' perceptions of autonomy. It emphasizes the impact of transformational leadership on teacher autonomy, fostering a positive organizational climate that encourages teachers to take ownership of curriculum decisions (Leithwood et al., 2016). Transformational leaders inspire and motivate teachers, creating a collaborative and empowering culture that supports autonomy in curriculum implementation. Another, a study by Smylie, Conley, and Marks (2015) highlights the importance of school leaders in creating conditions that enable teacher autonomy. School leaders who prioritize shared decision-making and provide support for teachers to exercise professional judgment contribute to a positive relationship between leadership and teacher autonomy. Specifically, the inferential analysis in Table 11 also highlighted the association between each factor of between the school leadership and the autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers in Tugbok District, Division of Davao City. Based on the same analysis, the Instructional Leadership indicator of the school leadership ranked as the top with a p-value of 0.000 and $-r$ -value of 0.660. This result implies that there is a strong positive signifi-

cant relationship between the instructional leadership of school leaders and the autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers in Tugbok District, Division of Davao City. This further suggests that the effectiveness of instructional leadership directly contributes to the level of autonomy teachers experience in implementing curriculum strategies. The findings affirm that fostering strong instructional leadership is pivotal for enhancing teachers' autonomy and influence over curriculum decisions. The presented result significant relationship between the instructional leadership of school leaders and the autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers aligns with various studies emphasizing the critical role of instructional leadership in shaping educational practices. Instructional leadership, characterized by a focus on curriculum development, instructional strategies, and teacher professional development, has been consistently associated with positive outcomes in schools (Hallinger, 2016). Also, instructional leadership significantly influences teacher efficacy and instructional improvement (Robinson et al., 2018). Moreover, Leithwood et al., (2018) argue that effective instructional leadership fosters a collaborative school culture, providing teachers with the support and resources needed to implement curriculum changes autonomously. Leaders who prioritize instructional improvement contribute to a positive relationship between instructional leadership and

teacher autonomy. This was followed by the Crisis Management indicator of the school leaders obtaining a p-value of 0.000 and $\neg r$ -value of 0.634. Still, this means that there is a strong positive significant relationship between crisis management of school leaders and the autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers in Tugbok District, Division of Davao City. This further suggests that the adeptness of school leaders in crisis management contributes positively to the autonomy experienced by teachers in curriculum implementation. The study underscores the importance of effective crisis management skills in fostering an environment where teachers feel empowered to exercise greater autonomy in shaping curriculum strategies. Ranked third is the Effective Communication indicator of the school leaders which obtained a p-value of 0.000 and $\neg r$ -value of 0.524. This means that there is a moderate positive significant relationship between effective communication of school leaders and the autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers in Tugbok District, Division of Davao City. This further suggests that the proficiency of school leaders in effective communication plays a moderately significant role in influencing the autonomy experienced by teachers in curriculum implementation. The study emphasizes the importance of transparent and clear communication from school leaders as a contributing factor to the autonomy granted to teachers in shaping curriculum practices. Relatively, the moderate positive correlation suggests that the perceived effective communication practices in Tugbok District positively influence the autonomy of public secondary school teachers in curriculum implementation. Effective communication is crucial in creating a shared understanding and fostering a collaborative culture within schools (Hargreaves Fullan, 2016). Also, according to Harris Hopkins (2018), effective communication is a key component of successful leadership

and positively influences teachers' perceptions of leadership practices. Lastly, the Data-Driven Decision Making indicator of the school leaders which obtained a p-value of 0.000 and $\neg r$ -value of 0.424. Still, this means that there is a moderate positive significant relationship between data-driven decision making of school leaders and the autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers in Tugbok District, Division of Davao City. This finding further suggests that the capacity of school leaders to make decisions based on data moderately influences the autonomy experienced by teachers in curriculum implementation. The study underscores the importance of fostering a data-driven culture among school leaders to enhance the autonomy of teachers in shaping curriculum strategies. Consequently, the finding aligns with contemporary literature emphasizing the role of data-driven practices in educational leadership. Effective use of data is increasingly recognized as a crucial aspect of school leadership, aiding decision-making processes and promoting instructional improvement (Leithwood Jantzi, 2016). Also, data-driven decision-making contributes to a school's capacity to enhance teaching and learning outcomes (Supovitz and Klein, 2013). Additionally, a study by Wayman, Midgley, Stringfield (2016) supports the notion that data-driven decision-making positively influences teacher autonomy by providing them with valuable insights into their instructional practices.

Regression Analysis of the School Leadership on the Autonomy on Curriculum Implementation of Public Secondary School Teachers

The last objective of this study is to determine which indicators of school leadership significantly influence the autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers in Tugbok District, Division of Davao City. The Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) is best fit for this analysis since this statistical treatment is defined as a predictive analysis

which is used to explain the relationship between one continuous dependent variable and two or more independent variables (Trek, 2019). Still, this data analysis is set with an alpha equal to 0.05. Shown in Table 4 is the regression analysis on the significant influence of school leadership on the autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers in Tugbok District, Division of Davao City. The overall regression analysis obtained a p-value of 0.000 and F-value equal to 44.828 which is higher than the set critical value. This means

that the school leadership has a significant influence on teacher’s autonomy on curriculum implementation. The findings emphasize the pivotal role school leaders play in creating an environment that fosters autonomy and allows teachers to shape curriculum implementation strategies based on their professional judgment. This further suggests the need for educational institutions to prioritize and enhance leadership practices to further support teacher autonomy in curriculum development.

Table 4. Regression Analysis of School Leadership on the Autonomy on Curriculum Implementation of Public Secondary School Teachers

School Leadership	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	B	t	Sig.
Constant	1.072			4.558	.000
Instructional Leadership	.303	.429	6.323	.000	Reject
Effective Communication	.075	.098	1.315	.191	Failed to Reject
Data-Driven Decision Making	.151	.169	2.572	.001	Reject
Crisis Management	.231	.321	4.362	.000	Reject
R	0.781				
R²	0.609				
F-Value	44.828				
p-value	0.000				

Interpretation: Significant influence of instructional leadership, data-driven decision making, and crisis management on teacher’s autonomy in curriculum implementation ($p < 0.05$).

Relatively, the regression analysis, revealed in the same table, brings forth a crucial revelation that three out of the four school leadership indicators significantly impact the autonomy on curriculum implementation among public secondary school teachers in Tugbok District, Division of Davao City. This empirical evidence decisively rejects the established null hypothesis, highlighting the concrete influence that specific aspects of school leadership wield over teachers’ autonomy in curriculum decisions. The identi-

fication of these influential indicators provides valuable insights for educational policymakers and school administrators to focus on key leadership areas that contribute significantly to fostering teacher autonomy. As a result, this study encourages targeted efforts to enhance leadership practices, promoting a collaborative and empowering environment for teachers in curriculum implementation. The comprehensive examination of school leadership indicators reveals a subtle difference of landscape where certain as-

pects significantly influence teachers' autonomy on curriculum implementation in Tugbok District, Division of Davao City. Particularly, the Instructional Leadership indicator emerges as a potent force, demonstrating a substantial impact with a high t-value of 6.323 and a p-value of 0.000. This finding underscores the pivotal role of instructional leadership in shaping the autonomy landscape, urging educational leaders to prioritize and enhance their instructional leadership practices. Similarly, the Crisis Management with a t-value equal to 4.362 and a p-value equal to 0.000, and Data-Driven Decision Making with a t-value equal to 2.572 and a p-value equal to 0.001 indicators contribute significantly, further emphasizing the various nature of effective school leadership in empowering teachers in curriculum decisions. However, the Effective Communication indicator with a t-value equal to 1.315 and p-value equal to 0.191, while not exhibiting a statistically significant impact, provides an opportunity for reflection and potential improvement, calling for a subtle difference in exploration of communication

strategies between school leaders and teachers to strengthen collaborative decision-making processes. Moreover, the substantial R-squared (R²) value of 0.609 derived from the regression analysis indicates a strong relationship between the leadership of school leaders and the autonomy on curriculum implementation among public secondary school teachers in Tugbok District, Division of Davao City. This implies that 60.9 of the variability in teachers' autonomy can be accounted for by the leadership practices of school leaders, underscoring the significant impact of their guidance. However, the existence of 39.1 unexplained variation suggests that factors beyond the considered leadership indicators contribute to teachers' autonomy on curriculum implementation. Future research endeavors should explore these unexamined factors to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the multifaceted influences on teachers' autonomy. This significant perspective can inform educational policies and practices that enhance teacher autonomy and, consequently, the quality of curriculum implementation.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

Presented in this chapter are the findings of the study based on the outcome of the gathered data. The conclusions drawn from the findings of the study are likewise outlined in this section. To maximize the significant contribution of this study, the researcher laid down recommendations in this chapter.

4.1. Findings—Effective implementation of the curriculum that is supported with good and effective leadership is crucial in ensuring that students receive a high-quality education that equips them with the necessary knowledge and skills for the future. However, striking a balance between teacher autonomy and adhering to a prescribed curriculum is a challenging task, one which is invariably affected by the leadership style and decisions of the school's management. The issue to which school leadership may be either facilitating or restricting

teacher's autonomy over their curriculum and teaching methodologies is critical for the ultimate goal of education which is to provide quality of learning outcomes. In this study, a non-experimental quantitative research methodology using a descriptive correlation approach was applied. Statistical analyses such as the mean, Pearson R correlation, and Multiple Linear Regression were utilized. The participants in the research were one hundred twenty (120) public secondary school teachers in Tugbok District, Division of Davao City. These respondents

were chosen via a sample process known as convenience sampling. Data were analyzed based on the survey questionnaires that were used by the researcher after they had been modified to conform to the parameters of the study, which had been subjected to validation by experts and had its reliability examined. Descriptive results of the study revealed that the extent of school leadership as perceived by public secondary school teachers received a high descriptive level rating which means that the extent of school leadership as perceived by public secondary school teachers is often evident while the extent of autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers received a high descriptive level rating which means that the extent of autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers is often evident. Consequently, there is a strong positive significant relationship between the school leadership and the autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teachers in Tugbok District, Division of Davao City. Likewise, the regression analysis resulted that instructional leadership, crisis management and data-driven decision making indicators of school leadership significantly influenced the autonomy on curriculum implementation of public secondary school teacher. Although some areas like effective communication did not show a statistically significant impact, they offer opportunities for further exploration and improvement.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were offered: The school leadership as public secondary school teachers is highly effective across various domains, including instructional leadership, crisis management, effective communication, and data-driven decision-making. This high level of perceived leadership quality contributes positively to the educational environment, fostering a culture of collaboration, trust, and effective management. Instructional lead-

ership stands out as particularly impactful, reflecting its significant role in creating a positive school culture and promoting effective teaching practices. Additionally, the recognition of leaders' abilities in crisis management and effective communication highlights their competence in navigating challenges and maintaining strong communication within the school community. The prevalence of data-driven decision-making further underscores the leaders' commitment to using informed strategies in their leadership practices, aligning with contemporary educational leadership theories. Relatively, public secondary school teachers experience a high degree of autonomy in curriculum implementation, with substantial independence in shaping curriculum decisions and instructional strategies. This autonomy is most pronounced in areas such as reflective practice, where teachers are empowered to critically evaluate and enhance their teaching methods. Additionally, teachers have significant freedom in choosing instructional approaches, adapting curriculum content to meet student needs, and designing assessment strategies. These aspects of autonomy not only reflect positively on the curriculum implementation process but also contribute to a more adaptable and effective educational environment. Moreover, there is a strong and significant positive relationship between school leadership and the autonomy of public secondary school teachers in curriculum implementation in Tugbok District, Division of Davao City. This implies that effective school leadership is a key factor in enhancing teachers' autonomy in shaping curriculum strategies, indicating a meaningful and impactful association between leadership practices and the independence teachers experience in curriculum-related decisions. Furthermore, the school leadership significantly influences the autonomy of public secondary school teachers in curriculum implementation in Tugbok District, Division of Davao City. This influence is particularly pronounced in specific leadership

indicators such as instructional leadership, crisis management, and data-driven decision making, each contributing in different ways to enhancing teacher autonomy in curriculum decisions. Also, the findings suggest a crucial role for school leaders in fostering an environment that not only supports but actively promotes teacher autonomy, highlighting the need for educational policies and leadership practices that prioritize these aspects. Although some areas like effective communication did not show a statistically significant impact, they offer opportunities for further exploration and improvement.

4.3. Recommendations—The following interventions were offered based on the conclusions of the study: The Department of Education officials may prioritize initiatives that reinforce these leadership qualities in public secondary schools. Specifically, there should be a focus on enhancing instructional leadership, crisis management, effective communication, and data-driven decision-making among school leaders. This can be achieved through targeted professional development programs and support systems that encourage the continuous growth of these competencies. Additionally, recognizing the positive impact of teacher autonomy on curriculum implementation, policies should be crafted to further empower teachers in their reflective practices, instructional strategies, curriculum adaptation, and assessment methods. The department may also explore ways to strengthen the relationship between school leadership and teacher autonomy, as this has shown to significantly enhance the educational environment. School administrators may focus on further developing and supporting instructional leadership, crisis management, effective communication, and data-driven decision-making skills among their staff. This development can be facilitated through ongoing professional development programs, mentorship opportunities, and the creation of a supportive school culture that values and encourages lead-

ership growth. Administrators should also prioritize and actively support teacher autonomy, recognizing its positive influence on curriculum implementation and the overall educational environment. This includes providing teachers with the necessary resources and flexibility to engage in reflective practice, adapt curriculum content, and develop their instructional and assessment strategies. Additionally, recognizing the strong relationship between leadership and teacher autonomy, administrators should foster an environment where these elements complement and strengthen each other, leading to a more cohesive and effective school community. Public secondary school teachers in curriculum implementation in Tugbok District, Division of Davao City are encouraged to actively engage in and leverage the autonomy granted to them. Teachers may capitalize on the opportunity to shape curriculum decisions and instructional strategies, using their professional judgment and creativity. Embracing reflective practice is particularly recommended, as it allows for the critical evaluation and enhancement of teaching methods. Teachers may also have urged to collaborate closely with their school leaders, understanding that effective leadership in areas like instructional guidance, crisis management, and data-driven decision making significantly impacts their teaching autonomy and overall educational outcomes. Additionally, teachers should seek to improve areas such as effective communication, not only to enhance their own practice but also to contribute to a more cohesive and effective school environment. Students in public secondary schools, particularly in Tugbok District, Division of Davao City, should be aware of the significant role and effectiveness of their school leadership and the autonomy of their teachers in curriculum implementation. Recognizing this, students are encouraged to actively participate in the educational process, engage in open and effective communication with their teachers, and take advantage of the

diverse instructional strategies and adapted curricula offered. This understanding can foster a deeper appreciation for the educational environment and promote a more collaborative and trusting relationship between students and teachers. Furthermore, students should feel empowered to provide feedback and communicate their needs and preferences, as this can contribute to the ongoing enhancement of teaching methods and curriculum adaptation. Future researchers in the field of educational leadership and curriculum development are encouraged to build upon the findings of this study, which highlights the significant impact of school leadership on teacher autonomy in curriculum implementation. It would be beneficial to explore further the dynamics of how specific leadership practices, particularly in areas like effective communication, influence teacher autonomy and educational outcomes. Additionally, there is a valuable opportunity to investigate the remaining aspects of school leadership that were not covered in this study, to provide a more comprehensive understanding of how different leadership styles and strategies affect various aspects of education. Research could also be extended to different geographical locations or educational levels to compare and contrast the effects of leadership on teacher autonomy.

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